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Data management plan (DMP)

Computer usage and neutron detection correlation between 2007 and 2017 in EU

EOSCSecretariat.eu

0. General information

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	21/05/2023	Final version of DMP – created for end of project (deliverable 21.05.20223)

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Project details

Project Name	Computer usage and neutron detection correlation between 2007 and 2017 in EU
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Contributors	Martin Ehrmann, ORCID iD: 0009-0001-0432-7145, Project Manager
Start date	2023-04-30
End date	2023-05-21
Funder, funding programme, grant number	-
Internal project number TU Wien	-

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
EU	European Union (time period 2007 until 2017)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier

Content

0. GENERAL INFORMATION	1
1. DATA DESCRIPTION AND COLLECTION OR RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA	5
a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?	5
b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?	7
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	10
a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?	10
b. What data quality control measures will be used?	10
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROCESS	11
a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?	11
b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?	11
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS, CODES OF CONDUCT	12
a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?	12
b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?	12
c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?	13
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	14
a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?	14
b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?	14
c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?	14
d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?	15
6. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	15
a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?	15
b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?	16

1. DATA DESCRIPTION AND COLLECTION OR RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

Reusing existing data:

For this project 2 external datasets will be used:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	nmdb_data.txt	https://www.nmdb.eu/	RL1	no
R2	ISOC_CI_CFP_CU	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/isoc_ci_cfp_cu	RL2	no

- **Dataset R1:**

Database citation:

- re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories.
- re3data.org: NMDB
- editing status 2022-05-31
- DOI: <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3PW80>
- last accessed: 2023-05-21
- Repository URL: <https://www.nmdb.eu>
- access: open access
- Policy and Licence:

RL1: Data retrieved via NMDB are the property of the individual data providers. These data are free for non commercial use to within the restriction imposed by the providers. If you use such data for your research or applications, please acknowledge the origin by a sentence like 'We acknowledge the NMDB database (www.nmdb.eu) founded under the European Union's FP7 programme (contract no. 213007), and the PIs of individual neutron monitors at: Athens (Physics Department of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece), Rome (SVIRCO Observatory, INAF IFSI-UNIRomaTre, Italy), IGY Jungfrauoch and NM64 Jungfrauoch (Physikalisches Institut, University of Bern, Switzerland), Lomnický štít (IEP SAS Kosice, Slovakia), Dourbes (Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium, Brussels, Belgium), Kiel (Institut für Experimentelle und Angewandte Physik, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Germany), Oulu (Sodankylä Geophysical Observatory of the University of Oulu, Finland)

For this research 8 different neutron detectors in EU-member countries will be selected:

Instructions for retrieving the data:

- Go to to the repository website <https://www.nmdb.eu>
- Read the data retrieval instructions under header Data and go to <https://www.nmdb.eu/next/>

- use the following settings for the data query:
 - Stations: ATHN, ROME, JUNG, JUNG1, LMKS, DRBS, KIEL, OULU
 - Date Selection (UTC) From: 2007-01-01 00:00:00 UTC
 - Date Selection (UTC) To: 2019-01-01 00:00:00 UTC
 - Resolution Time Resolution: 1 year
 - Data variables: Pressure & efficiency corr.
 - Scale: Counts/s*
 - Output: Ascii
- click an Submit
- select and copy the result starting with the line:

QUERY RESULTS SUMMARY

and ending (and including) the last line of data points. Do not copy the Total execution time line!
- save the data in an .txt file to your local clone of the source code repository with the name `nmdb_data.txt` in the folder `/input_data/data_raw/`

- **Dataset R2:**

Database citation:

- re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories.
- re3data.org: Eurostat
- editing status 2021-12-15
- DOI: <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3FW3X>
- last accessed: 2023-05-13
- Repository URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>
- access: open access
- Policy and Licence: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/about-us/policies/copyright>

For this research the whole dataset ISOC_CI_CFP_CU has been chosen.

Instructions for retrieving the data:

- Go to to the repository website <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>
- Enter `ISOC_CI_CFP_CU` into the search bar and select the first dataset
- Choose the dataset with the title *Individuals - computer use* and the code `isoc_ci_cfp_cu` and click Download data
- You should find a packaged file with the name `isoc_ci_cfp_cu.tsv.gz` in your download folder.
- Unpack this file and save it under the name `isoc_ci_cfp_cu.tsv` to your local clone of the source code repository at `/input_data/data_raw/`

New data produced:

In total 10 different new data objects will be produced:

- 1 GitHub repository containing source code in python and the two intermediate datasets
- 2 intermediate datasets which are produced by filtering, analysing and calculation of averages from the two reused datasets by the use of the python program in the GitHub repository.

- 3 output plots (two line plots, one bar plot) produced by the source code with data from the two intermediate datasets
- 3 raw data output files corresponding to the 3 output plots produced by the source code with data from the two intermediate datasets
- 1 Research report containing the description of the experiment, the data access and a discussion of the results

b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Computer_Usage_and_Neutron_Detection_Correlation	Archived data, Source code	.zip	100 MB	no
P2	Experiment Report: Computer usage and neutron detection correlation between 2007 and 2017 in EU	Standard office documents	.pdf	100 MB	no
P3	Bar-plot containing the increase in percent points of individuals (no age restriction) who have used a computer within the previous 3 months at least once sorted by their citizenship in an EU-member country over a period between 2007 and 2017	Images	.png	100 MB	no
P4	Dataset containing the increase in percent points of individuals (no age restriction) who have used a computer within the previous 3 months at least once sorted by their citizenship in an EU-member country over a period between 2007 and 2017	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no
P5	Plot containing the percentage of individuals (no age restriction) who have used a computer within the previous 3 months at least once. Annual data between 2007 and 2017 (excluding year 2016) averaged over all 28 EU-member countries	Images	.png	100 MB	no
P6	Dataset containing the percentage of individuals (no age restriction) who have used a computer within the previous 3 months at least once. Annual data between 2007 and 2017 (excluding year 2016) averaged over all 28 EU-member countries	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no
P7	Plot of annually averaged neutron detection per second, averaged over 8 European neutron detectors between 2007 and 2017	Images	.png	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P8	Dataset of annually averaged neutron detection per seconds, averaged over 8 European neutron detectors between 2007 and 2017	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no
P9	Intermediate (filtered and expanded) dataset containing the percentage of individuals who have used a computer within the previous 3 months at least once. Annual data between 2007 and 2017 over 28 European countries and the average over all countries. (only ment for recreation of the experiment if the original datasets are no longer available)	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no
P10	Intermediate (filtered and expanded) dataset of neutron detection samples taken between 2007 and 2017 (yearly interval) over eight European detection facilities. (only ment for recreation of the experiment if the original datasets are no longer available)	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no

- **P1:**

DOI for .zip file: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23011940.v1>

Link to the linked GitHub repository (also in the DOI):

[https://github.com/Fritzbert69/Computer Usage and Neutron Detection Correlation](https://github.com/Fritzbert69/Computer_Usage_and_Neutron_Detection_Correlation)

Size: 136kB

Programming language: python 3.8.10

Metadata: provided under the DOI

Folder structure:

```

├─ Fritzbert69-Computer_Usage_and_Neutron_Detection_Correlation-3a2330a
│   └─ data_input
│       └─ data_filtered
│           ├── Neutron_Detection_Filtered.csv
│           └─ PC_Use_Filtered.csv
│       └─ data_output
│           └─ plots_output
│               ├── anually_averaged_neutron_detections_per_sec_EU.png
│               ├── computer_usage_3m_EUsingle_line.png
│               └─ computer_usage_increase_10y_EUall_bar.png
│           └─ raw_data_output
│               ├── anually_averaged_neutron_detections_per_sec_EU.csv
│               ├── computer_usage_3m_EUsingle_line.csv
│               └─ computer_usage_increase_10y_EUall_bar.csv
│   └─ src
│       ├── data_model_tsv.py
│       ├── data_model_txt.py
│       ├── .gitignore
│       ├── LICENSE
│       ├── README.md
│       ├── main.py
│       └─ requirements.txt

```

- **P2:**

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23012267.v1>

- Size: 511kB
Pages: 13
- **P3:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22995644.v1>
Size: 26kB
Datapoints: 29 (Plot: 28 EU-member countries and the average over all 28)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P4:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22995434.v1>
Size: 1kB
Datapoints: 29 (mixed literal and numerical data: 28 EU-member countries and the average over all 28)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P5:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22995311.v1>
Size: 48kB
Datapoints: 10 (Plot: Annual data between 2007 and 2017 (excluding year 2016) averaged over all 28 EU-member countries)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P6:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22995071.v1>
Size: 1kB
Datapoints: 10 per header (Annual numerical data between 2007 and 2017 (excluding year 2016) averaged over all 28 EU-member countries)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P7:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22994390.v1>
Size: 57kB
Datapoints: 11 (Plot of annually averaged neutron detection per second, averaged over 8 European neutron detectors between 2007 and 2017)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P8:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22994054.v1>
Size: 1kB
Datapoints: 11 per header (numerical data of annually averaged neutron detection per second, averaged over 8 European neutron detectors between 2007 and 2017)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P9:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22990307.v1>
Size: 2kB
Datapoints: 360 in total including headers (mixed numerical and literal values, 28 EU-member countries per year, the average over all 28 per year, the increase for every country during the observation period)
Metadata: provided under the DOI
 - **P10:**
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22989275.v1>
Size: 1kB
Datapoints: 120 in total including headers (numerical values, 8 neutron detector stations and the annual average over all 8 stations)
Metadata: provided under the DOI

2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY

a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

For every new generated dataset standardised key words have been added to the DOI landing page in order make the data finable.

Reused data R1:

Metadata for every neutron detector station is provided under: <https://www.nmdb.eu/station/>

Metadata for the dataset itself is automatically generated and included in the file after submitting the query and should look like this:

QUERY RESULTS SUMMARY

#

STATION: ATHN, ROME, JUNG, JUNG1, LMKS, DRBS, KIEL, OULU

START TIME: 2007-01-01 00:00:00 UTC

END TIME: 2019-01-01 00:00:00 UTC

NMDB TABLE: 1 hour validated

DATA TYPE: corr_for_efficiency

AVERAGING: Yes / 1 year

ORIGINAL RES: 60 min

No standard metadata format could be applied to the dataset.

Reused data R2:

Metadata for the whole dataset is provided under

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/isoc_i_esms.htm

The metadata is standardised in Euro SDMX Metadata Structure (ESMS)

New generated data:

Metadata for the generated data is provided under each DOI with additional data under the corresponding reference within the DOI landing page.

No standard metadata format could be applied to the datasets.

Additional background information is provided within the research report under the DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23012267.v1>

b. What data quality control measures will be used?

Datasets based on R1:

The naming convention by <https://www.nmdb.eu/> will be used for the neutron detector station names. The format for the time measurement will be annually in yyyy. Notes about the method of measurement can be found at <https://www.nmdb.eu/> as well for every individual station.

Datasets based on R2:

The naming convention of the EU member countries by

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Country_codes

will be used for the neutron detector station names. The format for the time measurement will be annually in yyyy.

3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING THE RESEARCH PROCESS

a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

Data and metadata will be stored publicly available under the above mentioned DOIs and as an collection (Project) under https://figshare.com/projects/Experiment_Report_Computer_usage_and_neutron_detection_correlation_between_2007_and_2017_in_EU/167780 Additionally data P1, P9 and P10 is connected to a GitHub repository under https://github.com/Fritzbert69/Computer_Usage_and_Neutron_Detection_Correlation which ensures correct versioning of the data.

b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

No sensitive data (personalized data which is restricted by the DSGVO or data with restricted access policies) will be used during the project. All datasets are publicly available under a open access policy.

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
P6	writing	writing	reading only
P7	writing	writing	reading only
P8	writing	writing	reading only

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P9	writing	writing	reading only
P10	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS, CODES OF CONDUCT

a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

No sensitive data (personalized data which is restricted by the DSGVO or data with restricted access policies) will be used during the project. All datasets are publicly available under an open access policy.

b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23011940.v1	GPL-3.0
P2	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23012267.v1	CC BY 4.0
P3	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.22995644.v1	CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P4	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2995434.v1	CC BY 4.0
P5	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2995311.v1	CC BY 4.0
P6	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2995071.v1	CC BY 4.0
P7	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2994390.v1	CC BY 4.0
P8	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2994054.v1	CC BY 4.0
P9	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2990307.v1	CC BY 4.0
P10	Open	-	2023-05-21	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.2989275.v1	CC BY 4.0

Data-Owner of all listed datasets is Martin Ehrmann, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0432-7145>

c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

(Potential) ethical issues will be addressed (as far as they may occur) in separate documents according to the requirements of the relevant funding body. The DMP only serves to help identify some ethical issues. Please contact the Service Unit of Responsible Research Practices for additional information and support. Contact: Dr. Marjo Rauhala at ethics@tuwien.ac.at for additional information and support. You must do so if your planned research involves any human participation.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

All produced datasets are publicly available since 21.05.2023. The corresponding licences for reuse of every individual dataset can be found in the table under section 4b. There will be no embargo on the datasets.

b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

The Figshare repository offers a 10 year preservation of the individual datasets. Further information provided by Figshare:

Preservation and Continuity of Access Policy

All public research data published using the free version of figshare.com will not only live on Amazon Web Services S3 storage, but also be deposited into Chronopolis for further preservation. Chronopolis is a digital preservation service based out of The University of California at San Diego.

Figshare will use the DuraSpace DuraCloud Vault deposit node to add content into Chronopolis to preserve the public corpus of multi-disciplinary data. Chronopolis is a digital preservation network that provides services for long-term preservation of digital content. As a result, Figshare users can be guaranteed long-term access to their publicly available scholarly content.

For more information on Chronopolis and DuraCloud, please visit

<https://libraries.ucsd.edu/chronopolis/index.html> and <https://duraspace.org/duracloud/about/>

More information around our open archival information system (OAIS) model is available by request. If you're a research institution or Figshare for Institutions partner and are interested in exploring additional preservation workflow options, please get in touch at info@figshare.com.

Additionally the source code repository on GitHub was selected with the automated archive option.

c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

- P1:
Method: clone of the GitHub repository
Software: IDE with python 3.8.10 or newer and a virtual environment with the following dependencies:
 - contourpy==1.0.7
 - cycler==0.11.0
 - fonttools==4.39.4
 - importlib-resources==5.12.0
 - kiwisolver==1.4.4
 - matplotlib==3.7.1

- numpy==1.24.3
- packaging==23.1
- pandas==2.0.1
- Pillow==9.5.0
- pkg_resources==0.0.0
- pyparsing==3.0.9
- python-dateutil==2.8.2
- pytz==2023.3
- six==1.16.0
- tzdata==2023.3
- zipp==3.15.0
- P2:
Software: PDF-Reader
- P3:
Software: image viewer for .png images
- P4:
Software: csv-Reader or simple editor
- P5:
Software: image viewer for .png images
- P6:
Software: csv-Reader or simple editor
- P7:
Software: image viewer for .png images
- P8:
Software: csv-Reader or simple editor
- P9:
Software: csv-Reader or simple editor
- P10:
Software: .csv-Reader or simple editor

d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

Every produced data object will have a unique DOI and will be stored in a Figshare repository publicly available for a period over 10 years.

6. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

The responsibility for the data management and updating the DMP lies by the project owner Martin Ehrmann ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0432-7145> .

For this project no co-authors have been selected.

b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

To make the data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- The project owner will make the data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- The project owner will make the data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- The project owner will make the data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- The project owner will make the data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

No financial costs have arisen so far.

Considering the total amount of time spent in order to ensure that the data will be FAIR it is estimated that it will take about 48 hours of total working time.